

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16933677

Influence Of Staff Development Programmes On Academic Staff Performance In Colleges Of Education In North-East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated staff development programmes and academic staff task performance in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria". The purpose of the study is to investigate the influence of staff development programmes on academic staff performance in colleges of education in the North-East, Nigeria. two objectives were raised. Research question and hypotheses were raised in line with the objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design was employed for the study. The population of the study was 2728 academic staff. Multistage sampling was used to select the sample at different stages. Thus, the sample of the study was 759 academic staff. A self-structured questionnaire titled Staff Development Programmes and Academic Staff Performance Questionnaire (SDPASTPQ) was used for data collection. Three experts from faculty of education validated the instruments and the instrument was trial tested on 50 respondents in colleges of education Oju and Katsina-Ala Benue State which was not part of the study area but having same characteristics with the study population. Reliability index was 0.89 using Cronbach Alpha. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation as well as inferential statistic of chi-square. The finding of the study revealed among others that academic staff performance was positively influenced through staff development programmes such as higher degree attainment and conference attendance. Based on these findings, the study concluded that academic staff performance was positively influenced through staff development programmes, the study recommended among others that Since staff higher degree attainment improve academic staff performance, The management of Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria should implement policies that encourage and support academic staff in pursuing higher degrees (e.g., Master's and Doctorate), through sponsorship programs, study leave opportunities, and flexible work arrangements. This will enhance their pedagogical skills, research capabilities, and overall job performance.

Keywords: academic staff performance, staff development programmes,

INTRODUCTION

The constant curriculum modification and creation of new academic policies and programmes necessitate that educational systems continually train and retrain their academic staff. To this end, academic staff and development programmes become a foreseeable strategy that colleges of education should build in their system in order to survive in the current changing demands and accountability. Thus, since development

programs is a vital element to the survival and development of colleges of education and other higher institutions, colleges of education must carefully plan and implement staff development programs to muddle through these different pressures. Indeed, society has recognized education as key to human capital development and the system must be subject to reforms and repositioning because static education systems do not transform societies. (Lee 2013).

Education is the process of cultural transmission, values and accumulated knowledge of the society. Education according to Chukwuma, (2014), is a cumulative process of development of intellectual abilities, skills and attitudes, all of which form our various outlooks and dispositions to action in life. Education thrives in interactive and collaborative environment. It emphasizes active engagement, collaborative learning nurtures teamwork, hand on experience, communication skills, and preparing individuals for real- world challenges

It is obvious that education today aims at among others, the production of balanced human beings, who will be useful to themselves and the society. They are expected to make positive contributions to the society that offered them the opportunity to pursue programmes in education in accordance with the acceptable norms and values of the society which reflect in the law governing individual behavior. Generally, staff is regarded as the hub of educational development. Therefore, staff development programmes is concerned with the activities and courses in which serving staff may participate to upgrade their professional skills, interest and knowledge, subsequent to pre-training. However, staff development programmes are designed to bridge the gap of professional inadequacies of a serving staff. Osamwonyi, (2016) rightly states that staff development is a deliberate and continuous process involving the identification and discussion of present and anticipated needs of individual staff for furthering their task satisfaction and career prospects and of the institution for supporting its academic work plans, and implementation of programmes of staff activities designed for the harmonious satisfaction of these needs.

The society began to express general dissatisfaction with the existing education system and the concept of quality education in educational system. Every organization is expected to be committed in creating an enabling, equitable and motivating working environment; require adequate human and material resources to improve its social organization, preserve the culture, enhance economic development and reform the political structures. Thus, academic staff have important role to play to adequately prepare the young for their roles in the society in order to achieve the set national objectives (Okemakinde, Adewuyi and Alabi, 2013). Education is extremely important not only for the success of an individual but for the nation as well. Education is defined as the development of knowledge, skills and character of the students. Education is often seen as a prerequisite for quality manpower development and a sure path to success in life and service to humanity (Syeda, Nighat and Syeda, 2012). Education is a conscious and deliberate effort to create an atmosphere of learning and the learning process so that learners are actively developing the potential for them to have the spiritual strength for self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed themselves and society. (Akpakwu, 2013).

The Nigerian Federal Government in recognition of this observation has it that: the wide spread criticism in Teacher Education Programme (NCE Programme) is tunnel versioned, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) has revised and updated the existing NCE Minimum Standards in Colleges of Education in Nigeria (FRN, 2012) stated that, the Pre-Service Teacher Education curriculum content in Colleges of education and the University undergraduate programmes tend to be inadequate for the demands of a knowledge economy. The mastery of content knowledge in teaching subjects especially in Science and Technology is poor; teaching and learning materials are still inadequate and there is little or no skill development in the application of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) and modern media in teaching (FRN 2014).

There are varieties of delivery modes in colleges of education such as Sandwich Programme, Distance learning systems, Work and Study Programme. etc, each of these claiming to be delivering the same service to the Nigerians who are willing to acquire education anywhere and in any form. However, with the Proliferation of higher institutions in Nigeria today as a result of increasing number of school-age population who are already in school or are aspiring to be in school constitute aberration that impact

adversely on the educational system and have become part and parcel of the system. (Okwori, 2012). The utilization of both human and materials resources are necessary for the appropriate implementation of educational policies and programmes.

One may wonder why much emphasis is laid on quality education. There is ever growing concern for quality education in Nigeria because the country needs high quality education for its citizens. The reason is that the societies is changing and so are needs, and high quality education is a guarantee for greater quality manpower that leads to the derivation of high economic benefit for a better community and society in general. It is therefore necessary that quality manpower are realized, maintained, sustained and improved upon. However, the country economy situation and the political willing for quality education have necessitated the necessity for enough budget allocation to educational sector. Thus, management of colleges of education particularly in the North-East may be directly or indirectly affected by this action thereby limiting the possibility of subjecting their staff for training. (Afero, 2013).

The Federal Ministry of Education through the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) are responsible for quality control in colleges of education in Nigeria. The National Commission for Colleges of Education is entrusted with the responsibility of supervision of colleges of Education in Nigeria. Hence Decree number 3 of 1989 authorized NCCE to produce minimum standards for all programmes of teacher education and accredit their certificates and other academic awards after obtaining prior approval of the Minister. The 2012 Minimum Standard documents were based on the new mandate of the teacher training programme at the NCE level in Nigeria. The new mandate was to produce quality teachers. Thus, if NCE is to remain relevant to the subsector it is intended to serve, it must do more than it is presently doing. It is, therefore mandatory for Colleges of Education to prepare teachers with knowledge and skills required to teach effectively at the different levels of educational system if they are to remain and progress in their career (Ekpoh, Edet, and Nkama, 2013).

Staff members are the people who make up the workforce of an organization, the academic staff of any college of education are expected to bring about the competitive difference, since the success or failure of an educational organ is dependent on the quality of these resources. Academic staff are the competitive advantage which any college of education may have. This is because while equipment, infrastructure, methods of production, packaging and distribution strategies could all be facsimile by other competitive college of education, the innate quality, innovativeness, knowledge, abilities and skills of the human resource cannot be easily copied. Studies on human capital development revealed that it is the human resource of a nation that ultimately determines the pace of its social and economic development and not its capital or natural resources. (Lawal, 2014).

Staff development is a key to the success of any organisation as the smooth and efficient running of any organisation depends on how well employees are equipped with relevant skills to perform their task. It is a process designed to improve job understanding, promote more effective performance and establish future goals for career growth. Staff development is an activity that helps staff in understanding their responsibilities (Lifidi, 2015). It is the opportunities available to new and experienced staff to improve the quality of job effectiveness; enables individuals to grow professionally; introduce practitioners to the practical applications of research-validated strategies; and helps staff to meet their license and salary differentials. (Cobblah, and Van der Walt 2016). Staff development programmes can also be referred to as the processes and activities through which every educational institution, colleges, develop, enhances, and improves the skills, competencies and overall performance of its employees (Abu, 2012). This consists of the programmes, philosophy, aims and objectives and the curriculum which prepares the students to be competent in an area of specialization. This section inquires about the extent to which the institutional vision, mission and strategic goals of a given College of Education are sensitive and responsive to the production of well-motivated teachers with high personal and professional discipline, and integrity. This section also inquires about the quality of the various curricula of colleges of Education programme. It includes the general and specific admission requirement into Colleges of Education and graduation requirements. (Bello, 2014).

Staff development is a process that attempts to provide employees with information, skills and understanding of the school and its goals. It also aids an employee to continue to make the necessary positive contribution to the success of employees' school in terms of his/her good performance on the job. Lawal (2014) observes that staff development programmes are important aspects of development process that deal with the art of acquiring skills in areas that are relevant to their profession. The objectives of staff development programmes are to ensure the promotion of professional growth, improve pedagogical skills, keep teachers abreast of new knowledge, and meet particular needs such as curriculum development and orientation, leadership responsibility, new teachers to adjust to teaching field, promote mutual respect among staff and recognize the need for modern teaching methods. Notwithstanding, plethora of problems have been identified to militate against staff development programmes in Nigeria institutions particularly colleges of education in the North-East; one among these is that, development programme is capital intensive and most of the participants are self-sponsored. As a result, many of them cannot cope with exorbitant school fees and other incidental expenses for textbooks and personal upkeeps. Mohammed (2016) notes that many people after graduation have little or no opportunity for re-training to enable them develop themselves adequately to meet the demands of their job. Akinyemi, in Mohammed, (2016), open that, a well-designed staff development programme education could help to revitalize the practicing teacher or teacher managers, hence the need for continuing education of the practicing teacher.

Smart, in Peretomode and Chukwuma, (2014), Suggest that, the education of the teacher be made continuous, obligatory and undertaken at different periods. In Nigeria where the system of education is deregulated since 2003, couple with political interference, many institutions springing up tend to be having many unqualified and in-experienced teachers in their employment. So, if such are to be effective, the need to train and re-train staff becomes imperative and un-negotiable. The following objectives of staff development programme are identified to include:

1. To expose serving staff to the content and most modern methodologies of teaching.
 2. To make them prepare for new roles as Administrators, Senior Inspectors, Counsellors, etc.
 3. For serving workers who have to work in new areas at new levels with different types of students, there is need for in-service education to give necessary confidence and avoid trial and error.
 4. Teachers with out-dated teaching techniques, substandard knowledge of subject-matter and former teachers returning to teaching after a prolonged absence would need to update their knowledge through orientation and other staff development activities.
 5. It creates avenues for serving teachers to make up for their deficiencies in the area of newly-introduced subjects in the school curriculum like Computer Science, Test Construction and Evaluation Techniques, Record Keeping, Crisis Management, Peace and Conflict Studies, Coping Strategies and Caring for Special Children, First-Aid Education, Population and Gender Studies, HIV/AIDS Education, etc.
- Staff members work together through in-service programmes such as workshops, conferences, and higher degree, orientation/induction, seminar, symposium and study groups in areas of common interest in order to enhance their professional growth and competences. (Akpakwu, 2013).

Teachers constitute an important factor in the implementation of the curriculum. The quality of teachers is known to be a key predictor of student's performance. Teaching as a profession demands continuous development of knowledge and ability through training programmes. Such training programmes include higher degree, conference, workshop, seminars, correspondence, orientation/induction and mentoring staff. (Ingersoll and Strong, 2011). Pauline (2013), notes that many people after graduation have little or no opportunity for re-training to enable them develop themselves adequately to meet the demands of their task. In this study, the researchers considered degree attainment and conference attendance as the sub variables of the study.

Degree attainment is widely recognized as a significant factor influencing the professional competence and effectiveness of academic staff in higher education institutions. In Colleges of Education, higher academic qualifications often equip lecturers with advanced subject-matter expertise, improved pedagogical skills, and greater research capacity, all of which contribute to better teaching and learning

outcomes. Studies have shown that lecturers with higher degrees, such as master's and doctoral qualifications, tend to demonstrate stronger curriculum delivery, critical thinking integration, and mentorship capacity compared to those with lower qualifications (Eze & Nwankwo, 2020). Furthermore, in the Nigerian context, degree attainment is not only a requirement for career progression but also a determinant of credibility and influence within the academic community (Ofojebe & Okeke, 2019). This is consistent with global findings that academic staff with advanced qualifications exhibit higher productivity in research publications, student supervision, and innovative instructional practices (Adedeji & Adeyinka, 2021). Therefore, examining the influence of degree attainment on academic staff performance is essential for understanding how educational qualifications shape institutional effectiveness in Colleges of Education.

Akinyele (2017) carried out a study titled "staff development programmes and staff job performance in colleges of education in Delta state, Nigeria". The findings showed that staff members that were exposed to staff development programmes such as higher degree attainment among others were more effective in their jobs. Similarly, Ikoro, (2015) conducted a study on teachers' perceptions of staff development programmes as it relates to teachers' effectiveness: A study of private colleges of education in Lagos state. The findings revealed that teachers in the high performing colleges were found to take more interest in staff development programmes through higher degree attainment compared to their colleagues in the average performing institutions. The result of the study further revealed that during higher degree training programmes such as B.Ed or B.A. (Ed) or B.Sc (Ed) holders going for masters and master holders running Ph.D programmes that exist in full-time programmes. Teachers learn institutional management skills, evaluation techniques, academic achievement correlates and master wider content areas of their subjects. Additionally, Akinbode in Karabanick and Conley (2012) in their studies had established that investment in the form of in-service training was a crucial factor in the development and commitment. The result of their study showed that teachers who had low commitment to the profession prior to training became highly committed after they were given opportunity to go for in-service training. Thus, higher degree as an in-service training served to boost teachers' moral and thus, engendered positive work performance among them.

Conference attendance serves as an important staff development activity that exposes academic staff to current trends, research findings, and best practices within their disciplines. By participating in conferences, lecturers engage in professional networking, share research outputs, and gain exposure to innovative teaching and learning strategies (Bamidele & Olatunji, 2022). Such participation enhances academic staff performance by fostering continuous learning, improving instructional quality, and motivating scholarly productivity. Empirical evidence indicates that lecturers who attend academic conferences are more likely to integrate new knowledge into their teaching, publish in peer-reviewed journals, and participate in collaborative research projects (Nkang & Asuquo, 2018; Yusuf & Bello, 2021). In the Nigerian higher education context, conferences also serve as platforms for policy dialogue and capacity building, enabling academic staff to align their work with national education goals and global academic standards (Ogunyemi, 2023). Consequently, understanding the influence of conference attendance on academic staff performance is crucial for designing effective professional development policies in Colleges of Education.

Aroge (2012) conducted a study on the impact of conference and staff development on workers' job performance and optimal productivity in private and state colleges of education in Ogon State of Nigeria. The findings showed that conference and staff development had insignificant combined effects but significant relative effects on workers' optimal job productivity. Similarly, Ogohi, (2018) conducted a study on impact of professional development programmes on professional Librarians in colleges of education in South-south Nigeria. The finding revealed that conference attendance impacts professional librarians in their job performance through helping them maintain greater focus towards their job performance. It helps them stay up to date with new processes and procedures relating to their job. Additionally, Pauline (2013) carried out a study on the conference attendance needs of beginning teachers in state colleges of education in Imo state. The findings of the study indicate that beginning teachers who

attended conferences had better knowledge of colleges' policies, classroom management; operation of team work and time management.

Educational authorities and other stakeholder continued to raise alarm over the quality of products produced by state colleges of education in North Eastern Nigeria. Most graduates of these colleges of education who are supposed to teach at the elementary level of education today seem to be half baked as they can hardly plan and deliver lessons at the elementary level effectively talk more of teaching at the secondary level. Therefore, one wonders what could have been responsible for this fall in the quality of education in Nigeria in general, particularly in the North East Nigeria. Some stakeholders in education blame the teachers of these institutions for not being serious with their task of teaching and ensuring that students understand and comprehend their lectures as well as disciplining and ensuring that students are hard working.

Ashcroft (2014), argued that quality of education is further affected by variety of other forces such as: lack of competent staff, inadequate facilities, admission crises, poor human resources knowledge of curriculum content and methods of delivery, lack of good supervision and evaluation, poor management, and lack of adequate provision for all staff the opportunity to attend higher degree, conferences, workshop, orientation/induction, and seminars. According to Mohammed, (2012) higher education system are highly recommended to put in place appropriate staff development strategies to support all staff and promote involvement in the development and implementation of higher education wide policies and strategies. Therefore, it seems to be limited opportunity for all staff in attending such staff development programme to keep abreast with the current challenges. The need for staff in colleges of education in the North-East Nigeria to improve their knowledge, skills, attitude and behaviours while on the job is more critical now in the developing nation like Nigeria than ever before for a number of reasons for example, academic programmes in our schools rarely adequately prepared students as finish products for their future position as teachers and their accompanying responsibilities (Peretomode & Chukwuma, 2014).

Moreover, the issue of quality assurance to ensure credibility of certification is essential in staff productivity. Uche and Eukoha (2014), points out that teaching is a profession, therefore all who desire to work as teachers should be well groomed in the art of teaching. Brennen, in Uche and Eukoha (2014), asserts that new teachers are faced with several challenges upon beginning their teaching career; such as: class assignment, classroom discipline and management, demanding teaching workloads with assignment of extra duties, motivating students, dealing with individual differences among students, assessing students among others. Hence there is need to provide effective staff development programmes which will assist novice teachers as they begin their teaching career. Thus, the absences of opportunity for staff to attain development programme such as attending higher degree, conferences, workshop, orientation/induction and seminar may be a considering factor among others.

Mohammed (2012) posited that these entire training programmes can help both professional and non-professional staff to be current with new knowledge and development in the field. Also, given the deteriorating academic performance of college students, a lot of people, notable among them; parents, students and government have expressed dissatisfaction with the quality of teaching and learning that take place in colleges of education. He observed that teachers who were trained some few years ago are not adequately equipped for effective teaching except complemented by in-service training. To take care of the inadequacies of pre-service teacher preparation, the Federal Republic of Nigeria, in the National Policy on Education (2014), made provision for development of teachers by stating that teacher education shall continue to take cognizance of the changes in methodology and in the curriculum, and that continuous development programme for academic staff and non-academic staff shall be regulated. This therefore emphasizes the importance and the need for every staff to be constantly upgraded to keep abreast with the rapid changing society. This situation requires investigation. This study therefore, sought to examine 'influence of staff development programmes on academic staff performances in colleges of education in the North-East, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Students were not adequately prepared for life after school; Sound pre-service education cannot by definition ensure that academic staff will possess all the information, skills, and competence necessary for a lifetime of work in an academic setting. In educational organization, staff members' abilities and task performance are frequently the focus of attention. In Nigeria, staff development programmes is not systematically implemented and not coordinated in some zone including North-East, Nigeria. Little or no attention is paid to professional development of teachers. This could be evidenced by the lack of management, planning and initiative for training and development programmes for staff members. Consequently, the staff self-arrange for their further education, due to lack of resource, many staff members are unable to pursue higher education and thereby, lack competence. All these factors contribute to low performance in North-East, Nigerians colleges of education. This may lead to the lack of competence, and hence low staff performance

The growing concern is that staff members' preparation needs to be improved through training and retraining in order for them to be fully effective in carrying out their tasks in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, the need for continuous organization of staff development programmes to improve staff skills, knowledge, and competence in colleges of education in the North-East Nigeria is imperative.

Groups, parents, and other interested parties are lamenting the apparent underperformance of academic staff in the North-East colleges of education and are not meeting expectations and are not attending to the requirements of students and other stakeholders. Their performance continues to fall short of expectations, which has led to growing concerns about subpar overall academic performance, which is determined by how well their products perform in the education sector and other economic areas.

Furthermore, the use of modern teaching techniques to handle large class size and the information technology system in teaching seems to be a challenge to some teachers in this modern age, Kalagbor, (2016) documented that staff who attended development programmes may perform effectively as well demonstrate academic competence. These situations motivated the researcher to investigate influence of staff development programmes on academic staff performance in colleges of education in the North-East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to investigate the extent to which higher degree, attainment and conference influences academic staff performance in colleges of education in the North-East Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the influence of staff development programmes on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine:

- i. Influence of degree attainment on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education
- ii. Influence of conference attendance on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education

1.4 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the influence of degree attainment on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education?
- ii. What is the influence of conference attendance on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education?

1.5 Statement of the hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. Higher degree attainment does not significantly influence academic staff performance in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria
- ii. Conference participation does not significantly influence academic staff performance in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was employed for the study. The population of the study was 2728 academic staff. Multistage sampling was used to select the sample at different stages. Thus, the sample of the study was 759 academic staff. A self-structured questionnaire titled Staff Development Programmes and Academic Staff Performance Questionnaire (SDPASTPQ) was used for data collection. Three experts from faculty of education validated the instruments and the instrument was trial tested on 50 respondents in colleges of education Oju and Katsina-Ala Benue State which was not part of the study area but having same characteristics with the study population. Reliability index was 0.89 using Cronbach Alpha. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation as well as inferential statistic of chi-square. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic of chi-square. The mean score of 2.50 scores was used as a criterion mean score for decision making on each item. The mean score of 2.50 and above was accepted and below 2.50 was rejected as not having desired influence; while the chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question One: *What is the influence of degree attainment on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on the Influence of Higher Degree Attainment on Academic Staff Performance in Colleges of Education

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Sum	X	Std.	Decision
1	Staffs with Ph.D tend to be more upstanding with current educational challenges.	1836	714	114	5	2669	3.52	0.66	SA
2	Higher degree training improves task performance by effective lesson delivery.	1144	579	364	98	2185	2.88	1.06	A
3	master's degree training programmes exposes me to higher knowledge which facilitates task performance	1144	798	398	8	2348	3.09	0.82	A
4	Through higher degree attainment staffs knowledge is improved which enhance their task performance.	1708	777	126	10	2621	3.45	0.70	A
5	Through Ph.D training programmes, staff effectively communicates which enhance their task performance.	1048	696	404	63	2211	2.91	0.97	A
6	Staff acquired new skills through higher degree attainment which enhance their task performance.	1376	738	328	5	2447	3.22	0.80	A
7	Staff gets good mastery of their courses through master degree programmes training which enhance their task performance.	1216	876	306	10	2408	3.17	0.79	A
8	Through higher degree training programmes staff learn how to plan and deliver lesson effectively which enable them to perform better.	1232	699	410	13	2354	3.10	0.86	A
9	Staff that participate in postgraduate training programs stay more up to date with emerging trends which enhance their performance.	1632	771	172	8	2583	3.40	0.73	A
10	Ph.D training program increases staff competency which enhance their task performance.	1572	606	310	9	2497	3.29	0.83	A
Grand Mean							3.20	0.56	A

Source: Field Report 2023

Results of Table 1 show the mean and standard deviation scores of the rating items on the influence of higher degree attainment on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North East Nigeria. The results show that all the items have mean rating above 2.50 (test-value) from a 4-points likert scale. This shows that, the respondents seemed to be in agreement with the statements of items 2 to 10, and strongly agreed with the statements of item 1. In addition, the detail of the analysis revealed that the grand mean for the cluster is 3.20 which is greater than the test-value of 2.50. The grand means of 3.20 appear to show agreement with items 1-10, suggesting that more degree attainment favourably influence academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North East Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of conference attendance on academic staff performance in North-East Colleges of Education?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on the Influence of Conference Attendance on Academic Staff Performance in Colleges of Education

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Sum	X	Std.	Decision
11	Through conference attendance, academics staff acquires classroom control skills which enhance their performance.	1680	819	114	9	2622	3.45	0.69	A
12	Academic staff knowledge increase through conference attendance which enhance performance.	992	849	392	32	2265	2.98	0.87	A
13	Through conference attendance, academic staff learns new technological skills and how to apply them which influence their performance.	1236	810	346	7	2399	3.16	0.80	A
14	Conference attendance helps academic staff acquire technical skills which improve effectiveness in classroom instruction.	1048	954	330	14	2346	3.09	0.79	A
15	Staff attending conference tends to improve in conceptual skills which influence their tasks performance.	1176	894	294	20	2384	3.14	0.82	A
16	Academic staff is highly committed to profession when given the opportunity to attend conferences.	1032	606	472	63	2173	2.86	0.98	A
17	Conference attendance helps academic staff to develop problem solving skills for efficient task performance.	1304	813	278	23	2418	3.19	0.84	A
18	Conference attendance increase academic staff teaching skills.	1236	441	482	62	2221	2.93	1.02	A
19	Conference attendance improves	1388	501	374	58	2321	3.06	1.00	A
20	Staff communication skills/ability for higher task performance. Conference attendance mastery of area of specialization.	1416	645	336	22	2419	3.19	0.88	A
Grand Mean							3.11	0.61	A

Source: Field Report 2023

Table 2 displays high ratings for all items that fall above the 2.50 approved cut off point, which are 3.45, 2.98, 3.16, 3.09, 3.14, 2.86, 3.19, 2.93, 3.06 and 3.19 respectively, with correspondent standard deviation of 0.69, 0.87, 0.80, 0.79, 0.82, 0.98, 0.84, 1.02, 1.00, and 0.88. Given all ten items' mean ratings were

higher than the 2.50 threshold, it implied that; through conference attendance academic staff acquires classroom control skills which enhance their performance, academic staff knowledge increase through conference attendance, through conference, attendees learn new technological skills and how to apply them which influenced their performance, conference attendees acquired technical skills which improve effectiveness in classroom instruction as well conference attendees improve in conceptual skills and academic staff is highly committed to profession whengiven the opportunity to attend conference. The grand mean of 3.11 and standard deviation of 0.61 implied that conference attendance greatly influence academic staff performance in colleges of education in the North-East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One: Higher degree attainment does not significantly influence academic staff performance in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria.

Table 8: Chi Square Statistics on the Influence of Higher Degree Attainment on Academic Staff Performance.

Chi-square	df	P-value	Decision
344.797 ^a	21	0.000	Rejected

The chi square test= 344.797, $p > 0.00$, and $df = 21$ at the 0.05 alpha level were found on Table 8. The computed value surpasses the p-value, also the p-value of (0.000) is less than the alpha level of significant (0.05), on the basis of the data collected using Staff Development Programmes and Academic Staff Performance Questionnaire (SDPASPQ). Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, demonstrated that a higher degree's statistically significant influence on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Conference participation does not significantly influence academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria.

Table 9: Chi Square Statistics on the Influence of Conference Participation on Academic Staff Performance.

Chi-square	df	P-value	Decision
255.657 ^a	24	0.000	Rejected

The chi square test= 255.657, $p > 0.00$, and $df = 24$ at the 0.05 alpha level were found on Table 9. The computed value surpasses the p-value, also the p-value of (0.000) is less than the alpha level of significant (0.05), on the basis of the data collected using Staff Development Programmes and Academic Staff Performance Questionnaire (SDPASPQ). Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, demonstrated that conference participation had a statistically significant influence on academic staff performance at Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The main purpose of this study was to examine staff development programmes and academic staff performance in colleges of education in North-East Nigeria. However, the major findings of the study constitute the following:

- i. The finding of the study revealed a statistical influence of higher degree attainment on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria; the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, higher degree attendances significantly influence academic staff performance.
- ii. The study also found that there is a statistical influence of conference participation on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria. Because the null hypothesis

is rejected therefore conference participations significantly influence academic staff performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

The study examined staff development programmes and academics staff performance in public colleges of education in the North-East Nigeria

With reference to hypothesis one which sought to test how does higher degree attainment such as first degree, master degree and Ph.D degree programmes influence academic staff performance; the study revealed that there is statistically significant influence of higher degree attainment such as first degree, master degree and Ph.D degree programmes on academic staff performance in colleges of education in the north-east Nigeria in the areas of effective communication and new skills acquisition which enhance their performance. The study further revealed that academic staff gets good mastery of their courses and increases staff competency through higher degree attainment which enhance their performance. The finding agrees with that of Akinbode in Karabanick and Conley (2012) found that teachers who had low commitment to the profession prior to training became highly committed after they were given opportunity to go for higher degrees. In consonant with the findings of this study, Akinyele (2017) revealed that during in-service training programmes such as, B.Ed or B.A. (Ed) or B.Sc (Ed) holders going for masters and master holders running Ph.D programmes that exist in full-time programmes. Teachers learn institutional management skills, evaluation techniques, academic achievement correlates and master wider content areas of their subjects. However, the finding disagrees with Ikoro (2015), revealed that the various training programmes that are available in FCE Zaria did not impact positively in enhancing the skill, knowledge of the staff, and their performances on the job and service delivery. The ineffectiveness of the programmes had also led to the problem of staff retention in the college, especially among the highly experienced senior academic staff.

Considering hypothesis two for whether or not significant influence of conference participation on academic staff performance; the study revealed that there is statistically significant influence of conference participation on academic staff performance in Colleges of Education, in North-East Nigeria. The finding revealed that through conference participation academic staff acquires technical skills which improve effectiveness in classroom instruction. The finding indicated further that through conference attendance, academic staff learned new technological skill and how to apply them which enhance their task performance. Also, the result of the study revealed that through conference attendance academic staff increase in their teaching skill and improved communication skill as well ability for higher performance. This finding agrees with that of Ogohi (2018), found out that conference attendance impacts professional librarians in their job performance through helping them maintain greater focus towards their job performance. It helps them stay up to date with new processes and procedures relating to their job. The findings of this study is also in agreement with Pauline (2013), whose findings showed that teachers who participated in staff development programmes such as conferences were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of students' work. The outcome of this study is due to the awareness of the importance of conferences in improving job performance. However, the finding disagrees with Aroge (2012), showed that conference and staff development had insignificant combined effects but significant relative effects on workers' optimal job productivity.

CONCLUSION

Based on these findings, the study concluded that academic staff performance was positively influenced through staff development programmes such as higher degree attainment, conference participation, workshop attendance, orientation/ induction, seminars participation, mentor-mentee relationship and symposial attendance at colleges of education in the North-East, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Since staff higher degree attainment improve academic staff performance, The management of Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria should implement policies that encourage and support academic staff in pursuing higher degrees (e.g., Master's and Doctorate), through sponsorship programs, study leave opportunities, and flexible work arrangements. This will enhance their pedagogical skills, research capabilities, and overall job performance.
- ii. Because conference is desirable, and staff gains from this kind of training, therefore College administrators should institutionalize regular funding and opportunities for academic staff to attend local and international conferences, workshops, and seminars. This will enable staff to stay updated on emerging trends, share knowledge, and network with peers, thereby improving teaching effectiveness and research productivity.

REFERENCES

- Abu, M.M. (2012). *Manpower management: A hand book for personnel managers and students of administration*. Abuja: Ruth Books Nigeria Limited.
- Adedeji, T., & Adeyinka, A. A. (2021). Academic qualification and research productivity of lecturers in Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 25(2), 45–57.
- Afere, S. J. A. (2013). *Essentials of employee's task-motivation in the work environment. Some Important strategies of improving employees task performance, emphasis on education organizations*. Calabar: IBEPS. pp. 38-44.
- Akinyele, S.T. (2017). Staff development programmes and staff job performance in colleges in Delta state Nigeria. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 3(1), 112-130
- Akpakwu, O. S. (2013). *Human resource management in educational organizations. 3rd edition*, Makurdi: Eagle Prints
- Alabi, F. O. & Ige, A. M. (2014). issues in in-service education provision for teachers in Nigeria. The way forward in this decade and beyond. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 1(12), 126-132
- Aroge, S. T. (2012). Impact of conference on workers' performance and optimal productivity in private and state colleges of education in Osun state of Nigeria. *Journal of School Evaluation*, 8(2), 79-85.
- Ashcroft, E. (2014). Exploring the Relationship Between Staff Development and Improvement in Student Learning. *Journal of Staff Development*, 17(4), 1-9
- Bamidele, O. M., & Olatunji, S. O. (2022). Influence of academic conference participation on professional development of lecturers in Nigerian colleges of education. *Journal of Educational Development*, 7(1), 101–112.
- Bello, E. (2014). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, cause, and consequences*. 6th edition, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Chukwuma, O. (2014). Comprehensive paper on staff development. Retrieved on 21st April from <http://www.soencouragement.org/comprehensive-paper-on-staffdevelopment.htm>.
- Cobblah, U. & Van der Wait (2016). *Evaluating professional development of teacher educators in ethiopia: a case study of the higher Degree program at Addis Ababa University [M.S. thesis]*, University of Twente, Enschede,
- Ekpoh, U.I., Edet, A.O., & Nkama, V. (2013). Staff Development Programme and Secondary School Teachers Job Performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice Vol. 4, No 12,pp23-40*
- Eze, E. N., & Nwankwo, F. M. (2020). Impact of academic qualifications on the teaching effectiveness of lecturers in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Teacher Education and Teaching*, 18(1), 88–97.

- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education* (4th Ed.). Abuja: Nigerian Education Research Development Centre Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN,2012). Nigeria certificate in education minimum standards for general education. Abuja: National commission for Colleges of Education.
- Ikoro, F.M (2015). Teachers' perceptions of staff development programmes as it relates to teachers' effectiveness: A study of private colleges of education in Lagos state. *Journal of Educational research*. 1(1) 138-140.
- Ingersoll, R. & Strong, M. (2011). *Mentor-mentee needs analysis of academic staff for information and communication technology skill improvement for Beginning Teachers in faculty of education, college of education Igueben, Edo state. A Review of Education Research*. Vol. 81(2), 201-233. doi: 10.3102/0034654311403323
- Lawal, H. S. (2014). Mentor-Mentee relationship and staff attitude towards retention, motivation and organizational effectiveness in shahu shagari college of education, Kano state, Nigeria. *American Education Research Journal* 21(2)15-30.Retrieved on 23/05/2021 from : <http://www.iiste.org/Journals>.
- Lee, E. (2013). Higher education and Globalization-Challenges, threats and opportunities for Africa Maastricht: Maastricht University and Baston college.
- Lifidi Y.A.H (2015). Impact of staff development programmes on the performance of Teachers in secondary schools in Bauchi State. Nigeria master's thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Mohammed, A. H. (2012). *Developing Teachers: The Challenges of Lifelong Learning*. London, Falmer.
- Nkang, I. E., & Asuquo, P. N. (2018). Academic conferences and lecturers' professional growth in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(9), 213–224.
- Ofojebe, W. N., & Okeke, C. I. (2019). Academic qualifications as determinants of lecturers' performance in Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Higher Education Studies and Development*, 8(1), 56–68.
- Ogohi, D. C. (2018). Impact of professional development programmes on professional Librarians in colleges of education in South-South, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Business and Management*, 6 (5), 21-28
- Ogunyemi, B. (2023). Academic conferences as catalysts for quality improvement in Nigerian higher education. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Management*, 21(2), 67–81.
- Okemakinde, E., Adewuyi, O. & Alabi, E. O. (2013). *Producing Quality Teachers for National Development, Dr Aminu Ladan Sharefu's transformation of NTI*, published by NTI, printed by Yaliam Press Limited, No 3 Abeokuta street, Area 8, Garki- Abuja
- Okwori, A. (2012). *Management Issues in Education*. Makurdi: Aboki Publishers.
- Osemwonye, F. E. (2016). In-services education of teachers: Overview, problems and the way forward. *Journal of education and practice*, 7(26), 32-53
- Pauline, F. (2013). Conference attendance needs of beginning teachers in state college of education in Imo state. . *Educational Research and Review*: 8(2).125-137
- Peretomode, V. F., & Chukwuma, R. A. (2014). Man power development and lecturer productivity in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 8(13), 16-28.
- Syeda, F.J., Nighat, S., & Syeda, F.K. (2012) in Service Training: A Contributory Factor influencing Teachers: Teachers' Performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*. Vol. 1, No. 1
- Uche, S. C. & Enuokoha, O. I. (2014). Professional skills for effective teaching. Calabar: Stiffaith prints and supplies.
- Yusuf, M. O., & Bello, A. (2021). Conference attendance and research output among academic staff in Nigerian universities. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 20(1), 55–66.